

THE PRESENT CONTINUOUS TENSE

(Hozirgi davomli zamon)

Tursunov Jahongir Umarjon o'g'li

Farg'ona viloyati Uchko'prik tumani

1-son kasb-hunar maktabi ingliz tili fani o'qituvchisi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10655276>

Annotatsiya. Bu maqolada hozirgi davomli zamon shakli THE SIMPLE CONTINUOUS TENSE haqida va bu zamonning ishlatilishi, uning yasalishi haqida ma'lumotlar misollar orqali tadqiq qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Hozirgi davomli zamon, Present Continuous.

THE PRESENT CONTINUOUS TENSE

(Present continuous tense)

Abstract. In this article, information about the present continuous tense form THE SIMPLE CONTINUOUS TENSE and the use of this tense, its construction, is researched through examples.

Key words: Present Continuous, Present Continuous.

НАСТОЯЩЕЕ ПРОДОЛЖИТЕЛЬНОЕ ВРЕМЯ

(Настоящее продолженное время)

Аннотация. В данной статье на примерах исследуются сведения о форме настоящего продолженного времени THE SIMPLE CONTINUOUS TENSE и употреблении этого времени, его конструкции.

Ключевые слова: Настоящее продолженное время, Настоящее продолженное время.

1. Present Continuous to be fe'lining hozirgi zamondagi shakllaridan biri va asosiy fe'lining hozirgi zamon sifatdoshi (Present Participle) shaklini qo'yish bilan yasaladi:

Ega + am, is, are + Ving

Bu yerda Ving hozirgi zamon sifatdoshi:

I am working.

He is working.

We are working.

2. Bo'lishsiz shakli am, is, are yordamchi fe'lidan keyin not inkor yuklamasini qo'yish bilan yasaladi:

Ega +am, is, are+not + Ving

I am not working.

He is not working.

We are not working.

3. So'roq shakli gapning egasining oldiga yordamchi fe'lni o'tkazish bilan yasaladi:

Am Is Are + ega + Ving

Am I working? Is he working? Are you working?

4. Og'zaki nutqda quyidagi qisqartirmalar ishlatiladi: I'm, He's, She's, It's, We're, You're, They're, I'm not, He isn't, He's not, She isn't, She's not, It isn't, It's not, We aren't, We're not, You aren't, You're not, They aren't, They're not.

HOZIRGI DAVOMLI ZAMONNING ISHLATILISHI:

1. Gapirayotgan paytda, hozir sodir bo'layotgan ish-harakatni ifodalaydi:

He **is reading** a book.

She **is typing** a letter.

Don't make any noise, he **is sleeping**.

Quyidagi hissiyotni, idrokni va aqliy holatni ifodalovchi fe'llar davom zamonlarda ishlatilmaydi:

like yoqtirmoq

love sevmok

undersatand tushunmoq

remember eslamok

hate yoqtirmaslik, nafratlanmoq

want istamoq

wish, desire xohlamoq

forget unutmoq

believe ishonmoq

recognize tanimoq

see ko'rmoq

hear eshitmoq

feel his qilmoq

notice payqamoq

know bilmoq

seem, appear ko'rinmoq, o'xshamoq

possess egalik qilmoq

contain o'z ichiga olmoq

consist-dan iborat bo'lmoq

be bo'lmoq

2. Gapirayotgan paytda bo'lmasa ham, hozirgi zamonda uzoq vaqt davom etadigan ish harakatni ifodalaydi:

He **is writing** a new play.

That firm is carrying on nego-tiations for the purchase of ore.

3. If, when, while va boshqalar bilan boshlangan payt va shart ergash gaplarda kelasi zamonda davom etgan (Future Continuous o'rnida) ish-harakatni ifodalaydi:

If I **am sleeping** when he comes, wake me up, please.

I shall be reading the newspaper while you **are writing** your grammar exercises.

4. Kelasi zamondagi ish-harakatni bajarilishi aniq bo'lishi va gapda kelasi zamoni ko'rsatuvchi payt holi bo'lishi kerak:

They are going to the theatre tonight.

He **is taking** his examination on Friday.

We **are buying** a new radio set soon.

She **is leaving** by the five o'clock train.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, Present Continuous Tense – hozirgi davomli zamon odatda ayni paytda sodir bo'layotgan ish-harakatlarni ifodalash uchun qo'llaniladi.

Gapda egadan keyin am/is/are yordamchi fe'llari va asosiy fe'lga “-ing” qo'shilgan holda qo'llaniladi.

Bu maqolada zamonning ishlatilish usullari ham keltirib o'tildi.

REFERENCES

1. Cambridge English Skills Real Listening and Speaking 2 with Answers and Audio CD: Level 1-2
2. John and Liz soars. "New headway" (All levels) Oxford university.
3. Malcolm Mann. Destination (full set) Macmillan Education, UK-2013.
4. <https://teletype.in/@masofatalim/PresentCt>
5. <https://skyeng.ru/articles/7-osobennostej-upotrebleniya-vremeni-present-continuous/>
6. <https://www.native-english.ru/grammar/present-simple>
7. <https://t.me/masofatalim>